

*Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge,
H2020*

D2.7: Ontology testing and evaluation report; knowledge graph documentation and access interfaces (V1.0)

Deliverable information	
WP	WP2 Musical Heritage Knowledge Graphs
Deliverable dissemination level	PU Public
Deliverable type	R Document, report
Lead beneficiary	KCL
Contributors	KCL, UNIBO, NUIG
Document status	Final
Document version	V1.0
Date	30/06/2022
Authors	Albert Meroño-Peñuela (KCL), Jacopo de Bernardinis (KCL), Fiorela Ciroku (UNIBO), Valentina Carriero (UNIBO)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004746

PAGE INTENTIONALLY BLANK

Project Information

Project Start Date: 1st January 2021
Project Duration: 40 months
Project Website: <https://polifonia-project.eu>

Project Contacts

Project Coordinator

Valentina Presutti

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM -
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
Department of Language,
Literature and Modern Cultures
(LILEC)

E-mail:

valentina.presutti@unibo.it

Project Manager

Marta Clementi

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM -
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
Research division

E-mail: marta.clementi3@unibo.it

POLIFONIA Consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA	Italy
2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

The Polifonia Knowledge Graph (PKG) is one of the central contributions in the whole project, resulting from the integration of pilots' datasets and their interlinking with external resources. But while we develop the PKG, a key question to ask –which we address in this deliverable– is: how can we ensure that the PKG and the PON are of high quality? What kind of evidence can we show that the ontology modules and knowledge graphs in Polifonia are, indeed, adequately addressing the needs of the pilots? How can we automatically assess, through established –and novel– ontology evaluation techniques, that the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) and PKG are providing valid answers to the relevant competency questions?

Current approaches to address these in automated ontology evaluation, such as NeON Toolkit and TESTaLOD, are not entirely satisfactory: the former does offer iterative testing, but it only supports SPARQL-based competency question verification; and the latter provides Web-based testing supported based on the TestCase OWL metamodel, but only supports tests cases constructed by ontology testers.

To address these gaps, this deliverable introduces XDTesting, a tool support for testing ontologies based on the XD methodology. The tool is developed as an automation in the GitHub platform and is comprised of numerous features that are in coherence with the testing methodology.

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) - Institution
V0.1	30/03/2022	First draft released, outline	Albert Meroño-Peñuela (KCL), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL), Fiorela Ciroku (UNIBO)
V0.2	23/05/2022	Prepared for internal review	Albert Meroño (KCL), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL), Fiorela Ciroku (UNIBO), Valentina Carrero (UNIBO)
V0.3	20/06/2022	Amended with internal reviewer feedback	Albert Meroño (KCL), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL), Fiorela Ciroku (UNIBO)
V0.4	21/06/2022	Final version preparation	Albert Meroño (KCL), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL)
V1.0	30/06/2022	Final version submitted to EC	Marta Clementi (UNIBO)

Table of contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Related Work	3
2.1	Automating testing and current limitations	4
2.1.1	NeOn toolkit	4
2.1.2	TESTaLOD	4
3	Methodology	6
3.1	XD methodology on ontology testing	6
3.2	XD-based evaluation of the Polifonia Ontology Network	6
4	Implementation	11
4.1	Requirement collection	11
4.2	OWLUnit	13
4.3	XDTesting, an automated GitHub workflow	14
4.4	Technical development of XDTesting	16
4.5	XDTesting configurator app	25
5	Adoption and plan for evaluation	28
5.1	Expected impact on the community	28
5.2	Plan for evaluation	28
6	FAIR Protocol	30
7	Conclusions	31

1 Introduction

The Polifonia Knowledge Graph (PKG) is one of the central contributions in the whole project, resulting from the integration of pilots' datasets and their interlinking with external resources. The PKG is, therefore, built from datasets gathered internally (i.e. from the Pilots, see D1.1 [1]) and externally (e.g. public datasets such as MusicBrainz¹, and transformed in such a way that they adhere to the classes, properties and other resources modelled in the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) (see D2.1 [2]). Given the multi-modal and the heterogeneous nature of the expected outcome, it is fundamental that the ontology engineering process driving the construction of the knowledge graphs strongly relies on testing and evaluation. Therefore, a key question to ask –which we address in this deliverable– is: how can we ensure that the PKG and the PON are of high quality? What kind of evidence can we show that the ontology modules and knowledge graphs in Polifonia are, indeed, adequately addressing the needs that they are supposed to (e.g. requirements, see D1.1 [1])? How can we automatically assess, through established –and novel– ontology evaluation techniques, that the PON and PKG are providing valid answers to the relevant competency questions? To the best of our knowledge, little research has been done in devising tools and well-established methodologies for ontology testing and evaluation –especially those aiming at performing them automatically. This results in a considerable gap between software and ontology testing, where the former has witnessed the introduction and the establishment of a number of standard procedures and tools, such as unit [3] and integration [4] testing frameworks, to name a few.

The techniques and methodologies used for ontology testing vary based on: (i) the *stage* of the ontology development when they are applied, (ii) the *layer* that they test; (iii) and the *role* that they test. This has clear overlap with eXtreme Design (XD) [5] – an ontology design methodology that puts in its core the reuse of Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs), where the protocol developed for the testing of the ontologies is mostly descriptive. Nevertheless, the lack of tool support introduces considerable effort and time from the ontology testers. According to the XD protocol, the testing of the requirements are gathered in the form of stories from interactions with domain experts and investigations of the datasets that need to be modelled into an ontology. To test a single requirement, the current work of an ontology tester revolves around the following tasks: (i) selecting a requirement to test; (ii) reformulating the requirement into a SPARQL query; (iii) creating a JSON file to represent the expected results of the test, (iv) creating a test case OWL file and insert all the information; (v) creating test data and adding the reference to the test case; (vi) downloading and installing a JAR; (vii) running the test case in the local terminal or a SPARQL endpoint; and (viii) documenting the results. This process needs to be repeated for each requirement and it is particularly prone to syntax and semantic errors given its manual nature.

Another point that is worth to remark is the technical knowledge and skills required by the ontology

¹<https://musicbrainz.org/>

testing team, as the aforementioned pipeline involves defining SPARQL queries and interpreting their results, setting up local endpoints for testing, and defining test cases in OWL. On the other hand, the ontology design and testing teams in Polifonia are inter-disciplinary, and they also include people with little or no technical experience and background in XD; their involvement though, is key to ensure that the evaluation and testing process is aligned with the specific domain to which an ontology module pertains. In sum, the additional requirements entailed by Polifonia further ameliorate the complexity of the current ontology testing methods, and motivated the development of leaner, simpler, and collaborative procedures.

To address this gap, the deliverable introduces XDTesting, a tool support for testing ontologies based on the XD methodology. The tool is developed as an automation in the GitHub platform and is comprised of numerous features that are in coherence with the testing methodology. The features are identified from interactions with ontology engineers and testers and also from state-of-the-art tools and literature. A key advantage of XDTesting lies in the GitHub-oriented design of the tool, thereby leveraging the benefits of `Git` – a version control system that is extensively used for software development. In point of fact, the utility of versioning systems increases with the size of a project/repository and the number of contributors actively involved in the development. Therefore, not only does XDTesting accommodate the need of user-friendly tools for ontology testing, but it is also appealing for collaborative testing, and scaling with the number of collaborators and the complexity of the ontology(ies) under evaluation. The latter two properties – number of contributors and complexity of the ontological ecosystem, are both shared in Polifonia.

2 Related Work

The foundation of the tool support that we are developing is the XD ontology design and testing methodology. The methodology has been covered in several articles such as [6], [5], [7] where it is described in detail not only in the protocol but also illustrated with examples. The testing process in this methodology was/is to some extent supported by three tools NeOn toolkit, TESTaLOD and OWLUnit. We will describe each of these tools in detail in the sections below. XD is not the only methodology that supports the testing of the ontologies. In [8], the authors provide a classification of methods and tools for the evaluation of ontologies for industrial practice which gave us a basis of research about the field and a sense of classification of the tools that support the testing. Described in the report are methods such as OntoMetric [9], Natural Language Application metrics, OntoClean [10], EvaLexon [11] and tools such ODEval [12], OntoManager [13]. Another survey of the state-of-art of ontology evaluation is present in [14], where the authors classify the methodologies found into the following categories: those based on comparing the ontology to a “golden standard”, those based on using the ontology in an application and evaluating the results, those involving comparisons with a source of data about the domain to be covered by the ontology, those where evaluation is done by humans who try to assess how well the ontology meets a set of predefined criteria, standards, requirements. Similar classification can be found in another survey by Raad in [15]. Meanwhile, in [16], the authors present a model which consists of a meta-ontology, that characterises ontologies as semiotic objects, and an ontology of ontology validation called oQual, which provides the means to devise the best set of criteria for choosing an ontology over others in the context of a given project. In more recent work, the authors in [17] present a web-based tool called Themis, independent of any ontology development environment, for validating ontologies by means of the application of test expressions which, following lexico-syntactic patterns. While, in [18] Ławrynowicz and Keet introduce the approach of test-driven development (TDD) for ontology authoring. Their tool is implemented as a Protégé plugin so that one can perform a TDD test as a black box test. In another work [19], the development of TDDOnto, which implements a subset of TDD tests, is presented.

Mostly all the fore-mentioned works describe methodologies for testing and shortly refer to any tool support that exists to support them. A fact that we need to emphasise here is that, to our knowledge, the literature on the state-of-the-art primarily refers to dated tools, some of which are no longer actively maintained such as OntoManager¹ or at the worst case non accessible online such as ODEVal². This enforces, even more, our motivation to support the ontology testing process with tools and guarantee a certain level of ontology quality.

¹<https://github.com/lvS-KULeuven/OntoManager>

²<http://minsky.dia.fi.upm.es/odeval>

2.1 Automating testing and current limitations

Through time, there have been several contributions tool-wise to support ontology testing in XD. In the following subsections, we will describe in more detail two projects that have supported in the past the testing process, specifically the NeOn toolkit and TESTaLOD.

2.1.1 NeOn toolkit

The NeOn ontology engineering methodology does not prescribe a rigid workflow but instead suggests a variety of pathways for developing ontologies [20]. To do this, it proposes nine scenarios and further guidelines for reaching them for building ontology networks and general knowledge resources. These scenarios stem from all possible combinations between implementing ontologies from specifications from scratch without reuse, and reusing (or not), re-engineering (or taking as they are), merging (or keeping separate), restructuring, and localizing existing ontological and non-ontological resources and ontology design patterns. On the basis of this, NeOn proposes two ontology network life cycle models.

In terms of testing and automated testing, NeOn prescribes an iterative approach, as it establishes that “knowledge acquisition, documentation, configuration management, *evaluation*, and *assessment* should be carried out during the whole ontology network development, that is, in any scenario used for developing the ontology network” [20]. Over the years, various NeOn plugins have been proposed for automating parts of ontology testing; for example, [21] proposes XD Tool which integrates with NeOn and supports SPARQL-based competency question verification.

2.1.2 TESTaLOD

TESTaLOD is a Web application designed for providing the XD methodology with a testing toolbox for supporting knowledge graph testing [22]. It leverages the TestCase OWL meta-model³ as the standard schema for describing unit tests, as well as a way to validate ontology and data commitment. The tool is a two-step workflow powered by a Web-based user interface that allows a user to pick and execute an arbitrary number of defined test cases using the TestCase OWL meta model. A user must first give one or more test cases as input in the first phase. Those test cases can be simply uploaded from a local file system or fetched from a Github repository. TESTaLOD gets all test cases available in a GitHub repository by recursively traversing the subfolders reachable from the repository root when the user selects it. After all of the test cases have been retrieved, the user is presented with a view that allows them to choose whether or not to run all of the test cases in the repository. When files are uploaded from a local file system, however, all uploaded local files are tested directly. Both options provide a visual representation of the output of the automated execution of the selected test cases. The execution of a test case with TESTaLOD can result in one of three outcomes: (i) the test case is fully successful, and the corresponding record in the user interface is green; (ii) the test case is partially successful (the

³<http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/schemas/testannotationschema.owl>

test results do not match completely the expected results), and the corresponding record in the user interface is yellow; (iii) the test case is fully unsuccessful, and the corresponding record in the user interface is red coloured.

To conclude, TESTaLOD is a tool that provides support for the testing process by executing test cases that are already constructed by the ontology testers. As described in Section 3, the construction of the test cases is being supported by XDTesting – the proposed tool in this deliverable, which also executes and creates the necessary documentation of the execution. Moreover, to our knowledge, TESTaLOD has not seen active development in the last two years and does not currently provide certain features that would ameliorate the testing process, such as not being able to upload files or access GitHub repositories.

3 Methodology

In this chapter we introduce the methodology for ontology testing that eXtreme Design has laid the foundations of. We describe in detail the protocol that is used for testing a ontology module manually and the progress of testing for the Polifonia Ontology Network.

3.1 XD methodology on ontology testing

eXtreme Design intensively uses a test-driven approach as one of its main principles, alongside the reuse of ontology design patterns and the modular design of the ontologies. As such, several tests are created and executed to test diverse aspects of the ontology. In total there are three unit tests named competency question verification test (SPARQL unit test), inference verification test and error provocation test, and two higher-level tests named integration test and regression test. Specifically, competency question verification tests allow verifying if the ontology can answer the competency questions that have been selected during the requirement collection phase. Inference verification tests allow verifying that the inference mechanisms are in place, to ensure the correct fulfillment of the inference requirement. Error provocation tests allow verifying how the ontology acts when it is fed random or incorrect data. Moreover, the integration test allows verifying that the integration of an ontology fragment to a module has been successful. In this case, the ontology engineer shall perform all competency question verification tests, inference verification tests and error provocation tests of the module after the ontology fragment has been added. The regression test is the rerunning of all the fore-mentioned tests at the level of the ontology network, i.e. executing the tests of all modules that import the module where the ontology fragment was integrated.

Based on the literature, the protocol for testing only one requirement, i.e. competency question or general constraint, includes the following tasks for the ontology tester to complete: 1) selecting a requirement to test, 2) reformulating the requirement into a SPARQL query, 3) creating a JSON file to represent the expected results of the test, 4) creating a test case owl file and insert all the information, 5) creating test data and adding the reference to the test case, 6) downloading and installing a jar, 7) running the test case in the local terminal or a SPARQL endpoint, and 8) documenting the results.

3.2 XD-based evaluation of the Polifonia Ontology Network

Following the above-mentioned protocol, for each type of unit test, the ontology tester prepares a list of requirements that were collected from expert-driven or data-driven stories and are relevant

to the type of test. Following the principle of unit testing, they select one requirement to test in each test case. Then, the ontology engineer formulates the test procedure and creates, executes, and documents the execution of the test case. This procedure is followed until there are no more requirements to test.

The unit testing of the Polifonia Ontology Network has started with the Musical Performance module since this is also the module that was tested following application-based testing during the development of the SONAR demo. Considering that the tool that we propose is still under development and awaiting evaluation, the testing of this module has been carried out manually. For the competency question verification test, we have identified until now 25 requirements from expert-driven or data-driven stories, for which we have created test cases. For each competency question, we have completed its translation from natural language to SPARQL query, prepared an expected results file expressed in JSON, and created toy datasets to help with the execution of the tests. From these 25 tests, 19 has been executed successfully, 4 have not been executed due to a syntax error and 2 have failed due to the requirement not having been implemented. You can find the complete results of the competency question verification test in table 3.2. For the inference verification test, we have identified 10 requirements and are preparing the test cases by specifying an ASK SPARQL query, a reasoner, and a respective toy dataset. The requirements for these test are included the table 3.4. Lastly, for the error provocation test, we generally do not need requirements to create test cases, so we created only toy datasets that contain erroneous data. The documentation of the executed test cases is found in a folder named test, under the Musical-performance-ontology repository in GitHub.

In the listings 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, you can find an example of the input that an ontology needs to prepare before constructing a test case.

Listing 3.1: Competency question

Which recording is produced by a session?

Listing 3.2: SPARQL Query

```
PREFIX mp: <https://.../MusicalPerformance.owl>
SELECT DISTINCT ?recording
WHERE {
?session mp:isSessionOf ?recordingProcess .
?recordingProcess mp:producesRecording ?recording .}
```

Listing 3.3: Expected results

```
{ "head": {
  "vars": [ "recording" ] } ,
  "results": { "bindings": [ { "recording": {
    "type": "uri" ,
    "value": "https://.../MusicalPerformance/SPARQLUnitTest
/CQDataSet/ComeWithMe" } } ] } }
```

ID	Requirement	Result	Comment
CQ1	Where was a musical performance recorded?	Passed	
CQ2	When was a musical performance recorded?	Passed	
CQ3	Which performers have performed a musical composition?	Not executed	Syntax error
CQ4	Where was a musical composition performed?	Passed	
CQ5	Where was a musical composition performed for the first time?	Not executed	Syntax error
CQ6	Which recordings does a recording process produce?	Passed	
CQ7	Which musical performance does a recording process record?	Passed	
CQ8	In which release does a recording that is produced by a recording process belong to?	Passed	
CQ9	Which is the title of a recording produced by a recording process?	Passed	
CQ10	In which session is a recording produced?	Passed	
CQ11	Who are the agents that took part in the session?	Passed	
CQ12	What is the role of the agent that took part in the session?	Passed	
CQ13	What type is the session?	Passed	
CQ14	Where is a session recorded?	Passed	
CQ15	In which city is a session recorded?	Passed	
CQ16	In which District is a session recorded?	Passed	
CQ17	Which is the street name in which a session is recorded?	Passed	
CQ18	Which is the street number in which a session is recorded?	Passed	
CQ19	Which is the full address where a session is recorded?	Passed	
CQ20	Which is the type of the recording?	Failed	
CQ21	Which is the title of a release?	Passed	
CQ22	In which buildings was a musical composition performed?	Failed	Requirement not implemented
CQ23	In which buildings was a musical composition performed for the first time?	Failed	Requirement not implemented
CQ24	Which musician have performed a musical composition for the first time?	Not executed	Syntax error
CQ25	Which singers have performed a musical composition for the first time?	Not executed	Syntax error

Table 3.2: Testing of competency question of the Musical Performance module

ID	General constraint
IV1	Sound recording is disjoint with video recording.
IV2	A musical performance is disjoint with a recording.
IV3	A musical performance must have at least one recording process.
IV4	A release must have at least one recording.
IV5	A recording process must have at least one session.
IV6	A session must have at least one place.
IV7	A session must have at least one time interval.
IV8	A session must have at least one agent.
IV9	A session must have exactly one type.
IV10	A recording must have at least a title.

Table 3.4: Identified general constraints of the Musical Performance module

The protocol developed for the testing of the ontologies is thorough and detailed, but the lack of tools to support the process results in great effort and time spent by the ontology testers. Considering that the testing based on XD is done in units, certainly, the workload is even bigger because it is all carried out manually. Besides this drawback, when the test cases are created manually, the tester might encounter syntax and semantic errors in the process, prolonging it further. Since creating the test cases includes reformulating competency questions from natural language to SPARQL queries and creating files in JSON format to represent expected results as key tasks, the ontology tester should also have expertise at least in SPARQL querying. Having a testing process that is supported by tools lowers the necessity for high expertise and makes it more probable to being embraced also by people that do not have it. This might result in making the whole testing process a standard practice when developing ontologies because it will cost less time, effort, and expertise.

4 Implementation

Considering the remaining problem of lacking tool support in the field of ontology testing and evaluation, we are in the process of developing XDTesting, a tool support for testing ontologies based on the eXtreme Design methodology. The tool is developed as an automation in the GitHub platform and is comprised of numerous features that are in coherence with the testing methodology. The features are identified from interactions with ontology engineers and testers and also from state-of-the-art tools and literature. The main objective of the tool is to help ontology testers to create test cases (semi-)automatically and execute these test cases by using the current support that is an executable java jar named OWLUnit.

In the following sections, we cover briefly the process of requirement collection, describe OWLUnit and its capacities in the process of ontology testing and later go in detail about the workflows that are built within the XDTesting tool that support the creation of the test cases.

4.1 Requirement collection

In this section, we describe how we collected the initial set of requirements for the refinement of the existing tool support, OWLUnit, and the request for new features. In addition to the requirement collection, we present two small-scale surveys that we conducted to assess the state-of-the-art of the tool support for testing and the necessity of the testing automation in the GitHub platform.

We had a brainstorming session with researchers from STLab¹, a laboratory dedicated to the representation and processing of knowledge, to collect requirements for testing automation. Participants include researchers that specialise in ontology engineering and testing using eXtreme Design and have prior expertise with the OWLUnit jar. The purpose of the meeting was to explore how to improve the current tool support and add new capabilities to make ontology testing easier. The meeting resulted in the identification of the following action points.

1. The tool should enable the testing of an ontology module under development and not published under the official URI of the ontology.
2. The tool should enable the automatic rerun of all test cases when a competency question, SPARQL query, or expected result is updated.
3. The tool should enable the addition of an annotation property or a datatype property to specify the version of the test case.

¹<http://stlab.istc.cnr.it/stlab/>

4. The tool should enable the provision of detailed information in the response messages to understand why the tests fail.²
5. Create a test to check the consistency of an ontology. The tool should be able to run a reasoner, and assess the consistency of an ontology that has been provided by the ontology tester.
6. Create a test to check whether a SPARQL query, that is necessary to execute competency questions verification and inferences verification tests, is executable.

Following the identification of these requirements, we studied the possibility of automating the testing process using GitHub actions. We conducted a survey of existing actions and applications in the GitHub marketplace. The actions and workflows that we considered for analysis belong into the *testing* category. Aside from the category, another selection factor is the creators' accreditation, which ensures the quality of the tools. There are 927 activities and applications in the testing category in the GitHub marketplace, but only 37 are verified. We retrieved the URL, action name, description, originator, and review for each action and app. Following an examination of each of the 37 tools, it was discovered that there are no actions or applications that facilitate ontology testing. Beyond the restrictions, we looked for non-certified actions and applications in the Marketplace, but none of them allow ontology testing as well.

To justify our decision to implement the tool automation in GitHub, we performed another survey to determine the presence of repositories containing ontologies or tools for interacting with ontologies in the platform. On GitHub, we searched for the term *ontology* and found 9683 repositories. We analysed the Top 900 ranking of *Best matched* results from these 9683 repositories with the goal of classifying them to estimate the fraction of repositories that store ontologies. We divided the repositories into two categories: 1) Ontology repositories and 2) Ontology-handling/editing/visualisation tools repositories. The categorisation was done manually based on the description of the repository. If the description is lacking, the classification was done based on the repository's name, e.g. /example-ontology, or the repository's tag, e.g. ontology. To categorise the repository under the ontology repository, we considered terms such as ontology of, *example* ontology, ontology for, and ontology to explain. We looked for terms like tool, package, visualisation, code, manager, editor, and so on for the tool repository classification. Based on the sample under consideration, that is roughly 10% of the total results, it resulted that 65,8% are repositories that store ontologies and 34,2% repositories of tools for handling/editing/visualising ontologies. Ergo, we decided to develop from scratch an automation, comprised of several actions and workflows, in GitHub to provide tool support for the testing of the numerous ontologies that are stored on this platform.

Considerably, there are many online repositories and libraries such as BioPortal³, Ontology De-

²Currently the information that the ontology tester receives in case of failed tests are orderly Java errors or highly general messages that make it difficult to pinpoint the problem in the test case or dataset.

³<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>

sign Patterns⁴, OLS⁵, Obo-Foundry⁶, Ontobee⁷, etc, whose purpose is to store ontologies of a multitude of domains. Ontologies are also stored locally in private servers, public websites, and collaborative spaces. In contrast to these repositories, GitHub offers features that enable the possibility to have an early alpha tool support that can facilitate the workload of ontology testers instead of building API, web apps, and jars to interact with the fore mentioned repositories. Yet, making the tool useful also for other platforms is an aspect that is already identified and is being planned for the future development of the project.

4.2 OWLUnit

In this section, we present OWLUnit that is a java jar that allows the ontology tester to run unit tests for ontologies defined according to the OWLUnit Ontology⁸. This jar is the foundation upon which we have constructed XDTesting.

OWLUnit runs four kinds of test cases: annotation verification, competency question verification, inference verification, and error provocation verification. For the annotation verification test, it verifies that the tested ontology complies with its default ontology shape⁹. Alternatively, you can define your shape and specify it by using the `owlunit:hasShapes` property. While for the competency question verification test, OWLUnit makes sure that: 1. the IRIs used within the SPARQL query are defined either in the tested ontology or in the input test data (if provided), the IRIs that don't meet this condition are printed in the console; 2. (if input data is provided) the result of the SPARQL unit test query evaluated over the input data is isomorphic to the expected result. The expected result can be specified either as a JSON serialisation of the result set of the query or according to this vocabulary¹⁰. Moreover, you can also test multiple ontologies at a time. For the inference verification test, OWLUnit makes sure that: 1. the tested ontology is consistent, 2. if input data is provided, ontology and input data together don't lead to any inconsistency, 3. if a SPARQL unit test is provided, the result of the SPARQL unit test is equivalent to the expected result. Lastly, for the error provocation verification test, OWLUnit makes sure that ontology and input data are inconsistent together.

Listing 4.1: How to execute test cases with OWLUnit

```
usage: java -jar OWLUnit-<VERSION>.jar [ARGS]
# The URI of the test case to execute.
```

⁴http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Main_Page

⁵<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/index>

⁶<https://obofoundry.org/>

⁷<https://www.ontobee.org/>

⁸<http://150.146.207.114/lode/extract?url=https://raw.githubusercontent.com/luigi-asprino/owl-unit/0.2.0/ontology/ontology.owl>

⁹<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/luigi-asprino/owl-unit/main/shapes/ontology.ttl>

¹⁰<https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/DataAccess/tests/result-set#>

```
-c,--test-case <URI>

# The URI of the test suite to execute.
-s,--test-suite <URI>

# The filepath leading to the file defining the test case
# or test suite to be executed.
-f,--filepath <path>

# A list of pairs IRIs separated by a white space.
# The first IRI of the pair will be resolved on the second of the pair.
-m,--iri-mappings <A list of pairs of IRIs>
```

4.3 XDTesting, an automated GitHub workflow

XDTesting is a tool support that provides semi-automated management for unit testing of ontologies on GitHub by means of developed-from-scratch actions and based on the Continuous Integration practice. The fundamental features that are currently developed in the tool are: 1) Setup of the testing environment, 2) Crosscheck and parsing of the ontology tester input, 3) Construction and automatic execution of the unit test, and 4) Documentation of the unit test. Even though the workflows are developed using GitHub actions, we have facilitated the ontology tester by also creating a web application with the purpose of making the provision of the input more user-friendly.

The first artefact that we created is a use case diagram to identify the features that need to be implemented for the two different actors to perform. The actor *ontology engineer/tester* represents the end-user of the tool and the actor *system* represent the tool automation itself. As it is displayed in figure 4.1, the tasks that the ontology engineer or tester can do are to provide and modify the input. These two tasks are extended to other tasks such as providing the ontology, dataset, competency question, SPARQL query, and expected results. The ontology engineer can as well provide an ontology fragment name, analyze unit tests and merge Pull requests that are created automatically by the automation. On the other side, the system is able to perform several tasks. For instance, it can check whether all necessary input to construct a unit test has been provided by the user and check the syntax of the provided input. Moreover, it can construct, execute, document a unit test, notify the ontology engineer/tester of issues in Discord and create GitHub issues. To do so, firstly the system creates a structure of directory in GitHub for the ontology fragment, prepares the testing environment, and creates paths and URLs. To provide support for the Integration test, the system should be able to construct this type of test case and merge the ontology fragment to the ontology if all tests have been executed successfully.

The second artefact is the workflow of XDTesting, which uses many GitHub actions to perform the tasks mentioned above and is displayed in figure 4.2. The workflow is triggered when an ontology tester has the necessity to test an ontology fragment, that is a modelling of a set of

Figure 4.1: The use case diagram of the XD Testing tool automation

competency questions within a module. Based on the protocol, the tester needs to select a requirement to test and minimally have a toy dataset, with the extension of having a SPARQL query reformulation of the competency question and a file to represent the expected results of the query. This information can be provided to the workflow through the web application, which enables the tester to provide the name of the ontology module and fragment that they are testing, select the type of test that they want to create and provide the necessary input, and it displays the test case that is created in the back-end by the GitHub actions.

Meanwhile, in the back-end of XDTesting the workflow is listening to this input and as soon as it is received from the application, an action reads the information and feeds it to several other

actions. For example, it feeds the name of the ontology module and fragment to an action that creates a structure of GitHub directories to store the test cases and its results after execution, and it creates a GitHub pull request to insert the directories under the name of the fragment in GitHub. When the request is accepted by the tester in GitHub, an action that creates the test case is triggered. Before creating the test case, the action verifies if the tester has provided all the necessary input through the application and most importantly checks the syntax of the SPARQL query and expected results in JSON to catch syntactical errors before the test case is executed. If the syntax check is passed successfully, the action constructs the test case, otherwise, it will raise an issue to the ontology tester to check again the input. After the test case is created, another action executes it by using OWLUnit. If the execution is successful, the results are documented. If not, the workflow opens a GitHub issue and assigns an ontology tester to analyse it. Problems that are encountered at this stage are often semantic and therefore it might request for the tester to edit the input that was provided at the start of the process. Once there is a modification to the input, the workflow restarts the process at the stage of crosschecking the input. An online version of the diagram can be found here¹¹.

Figure 4.2: The workflow of the XD Testing tool automation

4.4 Technical development of XDTesting

The XDTesting tool provides support in several tasks that are crucial in the testing process of an ontology. In this section we will describe the features that are developed and already integrated in the workflow of XDTesting.

The *Read JSON file* feature is the action that makes possible the connection between the application and the GitHub repository. The action is able to read a JSON file that is produced by the application when a tester provides input for a new test case, sorts the information and feeds it to other actions for specific tasks. In the listing 4.2, you can find the details of the python code that is created to deal with the task.

Listing 4.2: Read JSON file

¹¹<https://github.com/FiorelaCiroku/XD-Testing/tree/main/Documentation/Test-Flow>

```
# Python program to read json file

import json

# Create variables to store values.
testType = ''
cq = ''
generalConstraint = ''
query = ''
queryFileName = ''
data = ''
dataFileName = ''
expectedResults = ''
expectedResultsFileName = ''
ID = ''

# Opening JSON file
f = open('XDInput.json')

# returns JSON object as a dictionary
data = json.load(f)

# Iterating through the json list
for doc in data['fragments']:
    #print(doc['name'], doc['ontologyName'])
    for item in doc['tests']:
        #print(item)
        if 'type' in item:
            testType = item['type']

        if item['type'] == 'COMPETENCY_QUESTION':
            cq = item['content']
            if 'query' in item:
                query = item['query']
            else:
                query = item['queryFileName']
            if 'expectedResults' in item:
                expectedResults = item['expectedResults']
            else:
                expectedResults = item['expectedResultsFileName']
            if 'data' in item:
                data = item['data']
            else:
```

```
        data = item['dataFileName']
    ID = item['id']

    #return testType, cq, query, expectedResults, ID

if item['type'] == 'GENERAL_CONSTRAINT':
    generalConstraint = item['content']
    if 'query' in item:
        query = item['query']
    else:
        query = item['queryFileName']

    if 'data' in item:
        data = item['data']
    else:
        data = item['dataFileName']
    expectedResults = True
    ID = item['id']

    #return generalConstraint, query, data, expectedResults, ID

if item['type'] == 'ERROR_PROVOCATION':
    if 'data' in item:
        data = item['data']
    else:
        data = item['dataFileName']
    expectedResults = 'error'
    ID = item['id']

# Closing file
f.close()
```

The *Ontology fragment directory structure* 4.3 feature's goal is to construct a GitHub directory structure for an ontology fragment that needs to be tested. The trigger of the feature is the receipt of the input from the application with the name of the ontology fragment that the tester wants to test. The action creates directories for each type of test, namely competency question verification, inference verification, error provocation, and a directory for the test documentation. There are two sub-folders for storing test cases and toy datasets in each test's directory. This whole task is done automatically and the tester only needs to merge the Pull request that is created by the action. In the listing 4.3, is displayed the complete action that has been developed and published in the marketplace of GitHub¹².

Listing 4.3: Create directory

¹²<https://github.com/marketplace/actions/create-directory-structure-for-xdtesting>

```
# The name of the action
name: Create directory structure for XDTesting

# Description of the action
description: Create a directory structure in a Github repository.

inputs:
  ontologyName:
    description: 'Name of the ontology'
    required: true
runs:

  using: "composite"
  # Steps that will be executed as part of the job
  steps:

    # Create directories
    - name: create-directory
      shell: bash
      run: |
        echo ${inputs.ontologyName}
        mkdir -p XDTesting
        cd XDTesting
        mkdir ${inputs.ontologyName}
        cd ${inputs.ontologyName}
        mkdir TestDocumentation
        mkdir CompetencyQuestionVerificationTest
        mkdir InferenceVerificationTest
        mkdir ErrorProvocationTest
        touch ${inputs.ontologyName}.owl
        cd TestDocumentation
        echo "TestDocumentation directory created"
        mkdir PassedTests
        mkdir FailedTests
        cd PassedTests
        echo "This directory stores successfully passed tests."
        > README.md
        cd ..
        cd FailedTests
        echo "This directory stores failed tests." > README.md
        cd ..
        cd ..
        cd CompetencyQuestionVerificationTest
        echo "CompetencyQuestionVerificationTest directory created"
```

```
mkdir CQTestCase
mkdir CQDataSet
cd CQTestCase
echo "This directory stores Competency Question Verification
test cases."> README.md
cd ..
cd CQDataSet
echo "This directory stores Competency Question Verification
test cases' data." > README.md
cd ..
cd ..
cd InferenceVerificationTest
echo "InferenceVerificationTest directory created"
mkdir IVTestCase
mkdir IVDataSet
cd IVTestCase
echo "This directory stores Inference Verification test cases."
> README.md
cd ..
cd IVDataSet
echo "This directory stores Inference Verification
test cases' data."> README.md
cd ..
cd ..
cd ErrorProvocationTest
echo "ErrorProvocationTest directory created"
mkdir EPTestCase
mkdir EPDataSet
cd EPTestCase
echo "This directory stores Error Provocation test cases."
> README.md
cd ..
cd EPDataSet
echo "This directory stores Error Provocation
test cases' data." > README.md
```

```
# This step creates an automatic pull request
for the directories that were created.
- name: Pull-to-master
  uses: peter-evans/create-pull-request@v4
```

The *Setup testing environment* feature takes care of installing the technical components required for the unit test execution on a GitHub hosted runner (server). The required components are Java

and the OWLUnit jar. A verified GitHub action named *Setup Java JDK*¹³ is used to download and install Java. Meanwhile, for the OWLUnit jar setup, we constructed a bash script capable of fetching and installing the newest version release of the jar from its GitHub repository. The action that implements the feature is shown in the listing 4.4.

Listing 4.4: Setup environment for testing

```
# The name of the action
name: XDTesting Environment Setup

# The description of the action
description: This is an action that is able to set up the environment
for unit testing in eXtreme Design ontology modelling methodology.

runs:
  using: "composite"
  # Steps that are executed for this job
  steps:
    # Sets up java
    - name: Set up java
      uses: actions/setup-java@v3.3.0
      with:
        distribution: 'temurin'
        java-version: '17'

    # Downloads the latest version of OWLUnit jar from the GitHub repository
    - name: Setup-OWLUnit
      shell: bash
      run: |
        curl -s https://api.github.com/repos/luigi-asprino/
        owl-unit/releases/latest \
        | grep browser_download_url \
        | cut -d : -f 2,3 \
        | tr -d \" \
        | wget -qi -
        echo "OWLUnit jar has been successfully downloaded!"
```

The *Construct unit test* feature is responsible for filling in the template for each type of test case. Since all the information that is necessary to construct a test case is present, what this feature does is match the competency question to the corresponding SPARQL query and expected result and insert this information in the template. Another essential part of the functionality is that it automatically constructs the prefixes that are used in the test case. The action creates a Pull request to add the new test case to the correct folder after the construction is finished. The

¹³<https://github.com/marketplace/actions/setup-java-jdk>

ontology engineer must merge this request into the main branch of the GitHub repository.

The *Run unit test* feature allows the system to execute a test case. The trigger of this automation is the addition of a test case file to any of the sub-folders that store test cases. The feature constructs the path to the test case and by using the Setup testing environment feature it executes the test case with the means of a bash script.

Document unit test is a feature that allows you to record the outcomes of a test case execution. The documentation of the test case is required for the entire testing operation. Despite the fact that GitHub gives an output of the activity, it is a good idea to keep this information for documentation. The documentation is created using a GitHub template that includes information like the requirement being tested, the test category, the test case description, the test itself, the input test data, the expected results, the actual results, when a test case was executed, the execution result, and the Run unit test feature log.

For specific information regarding the features *Construct unit test*, *Run unit test* and *Document unit test* you can access the GitHub repository <https://github.com/FiorelaCiroku/XD-Testing/>.

The *Check syntax* feature is used to verify the input syntax in specific SPARQL queries and expected results provided by the ontology engineer. We created a python script that uses the `rdflib` package to check the syntax of SPARQL queries. This library allows you to import namespaces like FOAF, RDFS, RDF, OWL, and XSD, as well as prepare queries for execution. The script prints "Success!" if the query syntax is correct; otherwise, it prints the error that occurred. In order to validate the expected results, we developed another Python script that imports the `JSON` module and can load the string as a JSON file. If the syntax of the expected results is valid as a JSON file, the script prints "Success!" and in the opposite, case it prints the error. The checking of the syntax of the SPARQL query and expected results are shown in the listing 4.5 and the listing 4.6.

Listing 4.5: Check SPARQL syntax

```
- name: Run SPARQL validator
  run: |
    function SPARQL_Validator () {
      validator_result="$( PYTHON_ARG="$1" python3 - <<END
    import os
    import sys
    import rdflib
    from rdflib.plugins.sparql import prepareQuery
    from rdflib.namespace import FOAF
    from rdflib.namespace import RDF
    from rdflib.namespace import RDFS
    from rdflib.namespace import DC
    from rdflib.namespace import OWL
    from rdflib.namespace import XSD
    try:
      q = prepareQuery(os.environ['PYTHON_ARG'],
```

```

        initNs={"foaf": FOAF , "rdfs": RDFS,
        "rdf": RDF, "owl": OWL, "xsd": XSD},)
        print("Success!")
    except Exception as error:
        print(error)
END
)"
    echo $validator_result
}
sparqlPath=" "
valResult=$(SPARQL_Validator "$sparqlPath")
if [ "$valResult" = "Success!" ]; then
    echo "SPARQLValidator=True" >> $GITHUB_ENV
else
    echo "SPARQLValidator=False" >> $GITHUB_ENV
fi

# A stop step that calls the cancel-action
to stop the automation if a condition has not been met.
- name: SPARQL Stop process
  if: ${{ env.SPARQLValidator == 'False' }}
  uses: andymckay/cancel-action@0.2

```

Listing 4.6: Check JSON syntax

```

- name: Run JSON validator
  if: ${{ env.SPARQLValidator == 'True' }}
  run: |
    function JSON_Validator () {
        validator_result="$( PYTHON_ARG="$1" python3 - <<END
import os
import json
import traceback
str = str(os.environ['PYTHON_ARG'])
try:
    json.loads(str)
    print("Success!")
except ValueError as error:
    print(error)
END
)"
        echo $validator_result
    }

    erPath=" "
    evalResult=$(JSON_Validator "$erPath")

```

```

if [ "$evalResult" = "Success!" ]; then
  echo "JSONValidator=True" >> $GITHUB_ENV
else
  echo "JSONValidator=True" >> $GITHUB_ENV
fi

```

```

# A stop step that calls the cancel-action
to stop the automation if a condition has not been met.
- name: JSON Stop process
  if: ${{ env.JSONValidator == 'False' }}
  uses: andymckay/cancel-action@0.2

```

The *Check toy dataset syntax* feature was developed with the goal of catching another type of error that could arise during the execution of a text case. We use this feature to see if the syntax of the dataset is correct. The check is carried out using a package named `Turtle validator`, installs the package, and then checks the syntax using the url of the dataset file. When the check is completed, the result is displayed in the terminal and it is used for further processing. These steps are shown in the listing 4.7.

Listing 4.7: Check Turtle syntax

```

# Install the turtle validator
- name: Run bash script
  run: npm install -g turtle-validator

# Check syntax of the sample dataset when provided an URL.
- name: Check syntax
  run:
    datasetUrl = " "
    ttl "$datasetUrl"

```

Lastly, the feature *Extract ontology fragment* is used to deal with situation when a change is done directly in the ontology module and not the ontology fragment. Through the `Git Diff` the action is able to get the changes that are done to the ontology module, understand the addition or removal of lines in the file and compile a new file with the ontology fragment only. This file is used for the modular unit testing of the fragment. More information is displayed in the listing 4.8.

Listing 4.8: Fragment extraction

```

# Action to get which files where changed after a push or a pull request.

name: Get push difference

on: [push, pull_request]

```

```

jobs:
  difference:
    runs-on: ubuntu-latest
    steps:
      - uses: actions/checkout@v2
      - name: Check for changes
        id: diff
        run: |
          if [ $GITHUB_BASE_REF ]; then
            # Pull Request
            git fetch origin $GITHUB_BASE_REF --depth=1
            export DIFF=$( git diff --name-only
              origin/$GITHUB_BASE_REF $GITHUB_SHA )
            echo "Diff between origin/$GITHUB_BASE_REF and $GITHUB_SHA"
          else
            # Push
            git fetch origin ${ github.event.before } --depth=1
            export DIFF=$( git diff --name-only ${ github.event.before }
              $GITHUB_SHA )
            echo "Diff between ${ github.event.before } and $GITHUB_SHA"
          fi
          echo "$DIFF"
          # Escape newlines (replace \n with %0A)
          echo "::set-output name=diff::$( echo "$DIFF" |
            sed ' :a;N;$!ba;s/\n/%0A/g' )"

      - run: echo "${ steps.diff.outputs.diff }"

      - run: git diff ${ github.event.before }
        $GITHUB_SHA > CommitChanges.txt

      - name: Pull-to-master
        uses: peter-evans/create-pull-request@v3
    
```

4.5 XDTesting configurator app

Parallel to the creation of the actions and workflows that are described in the section above, we have been invested into the development of an interface that serves as the front-end of the system. This interface is built using Angular 12¹⁴ and is able to do the actions showed in the list below. The XDTesting configurator has been published under the domain [testing](https://testing.polifonia.com).

¹⁴<https://angular.io/>

extremedesign.info and also published as an app in GitHub.

- The user can login using the GitHub authentication.
- The user can select the repository in which it desires to work on.
- The user can create new ontologies or select from ontologies that are found in the GitHub repository.
- The user can create new ontology fragments or edit existing ones.
- The user can create competency question verification test, inference verification tests and error provocation test for each ontology fragment.
- The user can write requirement and upload files for the SPARQL query, expected results and dataset for the competency question verification test.
- The user can provide a SPARQL query, select a reasoner and upload a dataset for the inference verification test.
- The user can upload the dataset for the error provocation test.
- The user can create the SPARQL query, dataset and expected results on the fly instead of uploading the files.
- The user can edit or delete the test cases.
- The user can check the status of the execution of the test case.
- The user can view the test case that is created and the documentation associated with it.
- The user can be notified of GitHub issues that are created in the case of an unsuccessful execution of a test case.
- The user can view the list and progress of the actions running in the selected repository.
- The user can be informed about the methodology and the usage of the tool in the Help section.

In the picture 4.3 is shown the primary view the XDTesting configurator. As you can see from the picture, in the left side panel are the sections of Ontologies, Ontology fragments, GitHub actions and Help. While in the right side, the user can select to create a new ontology or to use one of the existing ones. The Ontology Fragments section is displayed in 4.4. In this view of the interface, the user can create a new ontology fragment or use the ones on the list. If he/she decides to select one, then the user is directed to the view shown in 4.5. Here, the user can check the status of execution of the existing test cases or provide the input for the creation of a new one. In each of the view, the user can find quick information regarding important term and concept by hovering on the information bubbles. For a more detailed information, he can redirect to the Help section of the configurator.

Currently, we have under development the creation of a dashboard to aesthetically display the results of the test case executions and important statistics regarding the ontology testing of a module.

Figure 4.3: The primary view of the XDTTesting configurator

Figure 4.4: The Ontology Fragment section of the XDTTesting configurator

Figure 4.5: The test case view of the XDTTesting configurator

5 Adoption and plan for evaluation

In this chapter, we discuss the impact that XDTesting, as a tool support for ontology testing, is expected to have on the Semantic Web community. Moreover, we describe the steps that we are taking for the technical evaluation of the tool and a user-based evaluation as well in order to assess the quality of the tool and identify bugs and new feature requests.

5.1 Expected impact on the community

XD Testing is a tool designed to assist with the testing phase of the ontology engineering process. The tool itself aims to meet an immediate need for support in this field while also contributing to the research community by encouraging and standardising ontology testing as a process. With this tool, we expect to release the ontology testers from the burden of manually creating, running and documenting unit test cases for modules by providing an easy-to-use interface for sending input and a workflow of GitHub actions to perform tasks that guarantee the successful construction and execution of test cases. In overall, the tool is expected to minimise the time, effort, and expertise required by the ontology tester.

Another important aspect is that even though the tool is being developed based on the XD ontology modelling methodology, we are already expanding its capabilities to deal with unit testing of ontologies that are not modelled following XD principles. An example of this expansion is the *Extract ontology fragment* feature described in the section above. So, a tester does not need to have an extensive knowledge of the eXtreme Design testing methodology to be able to use it for evaluating its ontologies. This expansion is also valuable to test ontologies that are not built using the modular design as an approach.

Ultimately, we expect to increase the impact of the tool on the community by making the tool independent of the GitHub platform. This approach can make the tool useful to test ontologies that are stored in other platforms, own servers, etc. We are considering options such as self-hosted servers, cloud-hosted management, and platform expansion. At this point in the project, we are thoroughly discussing the benefits and drawbacks of each option and have yet to reach a decision about the next action point in this direction.

5.2 Plan for evaluation

The evaluation plan of XDTesting is two-fold: (i) the technical testing of the tool, and (ii) the usability and adaption by ontology testers. The technical testing of XDTesting is separated into two main tasks that are the testing of the web application and the testing of the Github workflow

and actions. The testing of the web application is straightforward and it is performed using unit tests as in any software engineering project. For the testing of the Github workflow and actions, there are no standard practices and therefore we are creating tests to assess the quality. Most of these tests consist of feeding the workflow incomplete, erroneous, missing, edge, overloaded, and correct input. For example, we provide a SPARQL query not syntactically correct to check whether the action that checks the syntax is able to catch the error and raise an issue to notify the tester about the error.

On the other side, there is the user-based evaluation of the tool. The evaluation will take the shape of a testing session, which will be carried out in cooperation with ontology engineers and testers. They will be introduced to the tool first, which is detailed in the instructions. We will next provide the task that the participants must do throughout the session, as well as directions on how to complete it. We've created an ontology fragment, a competency question with the respective SPARQL query and expected result, general constraints, and datasets for the exercise. All this information is displayed in this GitHub page¹. To document the problems that the participants will encounter during the session we have created two GitHub issue templates. One template is to document reports for bugs and the other for requesting features that they would like to have. We have also opened several discussion boards² to light up conversations regarding features, bugs, documentation, and general feedback.

¹<https://fiorelaciroku.github.io/XD-Testing/>

²<https://github.com/FiorelaCiroku/XD-Testing/discussions>

6 FAIR Protocol

The following outputs have been released as a result of the work described in this deliverable:

1. XDTesting infrastructure¹

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [23]. In particular, via GitHub the XDTesting infrastructure has a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source. Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook² [1], the XDTesting infrastructure will be integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described, machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. The storage of all resources on Github guarantees their persistence beyond the project. Additionally, the very architecture of XDTesting relies on GitHub actions, which can be seen as provenance execution traces –a possible mapping of these actions into interoperable provenance representations, such as PROV [24], is planned for the future.

Being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The resources created by the XDTesting framework will be released in the future as an RDF knowledge graph.

Finally, XDTesting is released with a CC–BY 4.0 licence that allows all resources to be copied and redistributed in any medium or format. The material may also be remixed, transformed, and build upon for any purpose, even commercially.

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/XD-Testing>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

7 Conclusions

The evaluation and testing of ontology modules are fundamental steps in the ontology engineering process, as they are meant to quantify the ability of the ontological infrastructure to: effectively address and cover the competency questions that motivated and guided the design of the ontology; support inference by means of logical reasoning; and be robust against errors. In this deliverable, we presented a novel methodology for XD Testing tool automation, which is currently in use for testing the ontology modules that are part of the Polifonia Ontology Network. One of the benefits of the proposed testing method is its ease of use, which decreases the technical barriers of traditional ontology testing, as it can be potentially used by non-experts. This advantage is particularly appealing for Polifonia, given that people without considerable knowledge and expertise with Semantic Web technologies (e.g. SPARQL) are directly involved in the ontology design activities, mainly due to their extensive musical background.

Now that a testing methodology that meets the specific needs of the project has been put forth, we are currently conducting an extensive evaluation of all the ontology modules in PON. This is also contributing to the extension of the proposed tool based on the feedback that is incrementally collected during such process. Considering the novelty of the proposed testing methodology, we are also seeking collaborative efforts in the ontology testing community in order to encourage testing as a standard practice in the data engineering process.

Bibliography

- [1] C. Guillotel-Nothmann, “Knowledge extraction and modelling in the project thesaurus musicarum germanicarum,” in *Prague DH Workshops Session III: Editions*, 2020.
- [2] A. Meroño Peñuela, C. Guillotel-Nothmann, J. de Berardinis, D. Sol Martinez Pandiani, V. Anita Carriero, M. Wigham, A. Poltronieri, F. Ciroku, and P. Rigaux, “D2.1 ontology-based knowledge graphs for music objects 1st version,” European Commission, The Polifonia consortium, Tech. Rep., 2021.
- [3] P. Runeson, “A survey of unit testing practices,” *IEEE software*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 22–29, 2006.
- [4] P. C. Jorgensen and C. Erickson, “Object-oriented integration testing,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 30–38, 1994.
- [5] V. Presutti, E. Daga, A. Gangemi, and E. Blomqvist, “extreme design with content ontology design patterns,” in *Proc. Workshop on Ontology Patterns*, 2009, pp. 83–97.
- [6] E. Blomqvist, V. Presutti, E. Daga, and A. Gangemi, “Experimenting with extreme design,” in *International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management*. Springer, 2010, pp. 120–134.
- [7] E. Blomqvist, K. Hammar, and V. Presutti, “Engineering ontologies with patterns—the extreme design methodology.” *Ontology Engineering with Ontology Design Patterns*, no. 25, pp. 23–50, 2016.
- [8] J. Hartmann, P. Spyns, A. Giboin, D. Maynard, R. Cuel, M. Suarez-Figeroa, and Y. Sure, “Methods for ontology evaluation.” 2005.
- [9] B. Lantow, “Ontometrics: Putting metrics into use for ontology evaluation.” in *KEOD*, 2016, pp. 186–191.
- [10] N. Guarino and C. A. Welty, “An overview of ontoclean,” *Handbook on ontologies*, pp. 151–171, 2004.
- [11] P. Spyns, “Validating evalexon: validating a tool for evaluating automatically lexical triples mined from texts,” 2007.
- [12] Ó. Corcho, A. Gómez-Pérez, R. González-Cabero, and M. C. Suárez-Figueroa, “Odeval: a tool for evaluating rdf (s), daml+ oil, and owl concept taxonomies,” in *IFIP International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations*. Springer, 2004, pp. 369–382.
- [13] L. Stojanovic, N. Stojanovic, J. Gonzalez, and R. Studer, “Ontomanager—a system for the usage-based ontology management,” in *OTM Confederated International Conferences” On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems”*. Springer, 2003, pp. 858–875.
- [14] J. Brank, M. Grobelnik, and D. Mladenic, “A survey of ontology evaluation techniques,” in

Proceedings of the conference on data mining and data warehouses (SiKDD 2005). Cite-seer Ljubljana Slovenia, 2005, pp. 166–170.

- [15] J. Raad and C. Cruz, “A survey on ontology evaluation methods,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Ontology Development, part of the 7th International Joint Conference on Knowledge Discovery, Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management*, 2015.
- [16] A. Gangemi, C. Catenacci, M. Ciaramita, and J. Lehmann, “Modelling ontology evaluation and validation,” in *European Semantic Web Conference*. Springer, 2006, pp. 140–154.
- [17] A. Fernández-Izquierdo and R. García-Castro, “Themis: a tool for validating ontologies through requirements.” in *SEKE*, 2019, pp. 573–753.
- [18] C. M. Keet and A. Ławrynowicz, “Test-driven development of ontologies,” in *European Semantic Web Conference*. Springer, 2016, pp. 642–657.
- [19] A. Lawrynowicz and C. M. Keet, “The tddonto tool for test-driven development of dl knowledge bases,” 2016.
- [20] M. C. Suárez-Figueroa, A. Gómez-Pérez, and M. Fernández-López, “The neon methodology for ontology engineering,” in *Ontology engineering in a networked world*. Springer, 2012, pp. 9–34.
- [21] E. Blomqvist, A. Seil Sepour, and V. Presutti, “Ontology testing-methodology and tool,” in *International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management*. Springer, 2012, pp. 216–226.
- [22] V. A. Carriero, F. Mariani, A. G. Nuzzolese, V. Pasqual, and V. Presutti, “Agile knowledge graph testing with testalod.” in *ISWC Satellites*, 2019, pp. 221–224.
- [23] M. D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, N. Blomberg, J.-W. Boiten, L. B. da Silva Santos, P. E. Bourne *et al.*, “The fair guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship,” *Scientific data*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2016.
- [24] P. Groth and L. Moreau, “Prov-overview,” *W3C Working Group Note*, 2013.